

Attachment to the Study Report:

Collection of Guided Questions for Interviews, Drawing and Participatory Mapping sessions with Tokou Fisherwomen

Theme 1: Personal Background

1. Are you the eldest in your family? If not, how many siblings do you have?
2. Have you always lived here, or did you arrive/marry into Tokou?/ study site (other village)
3. When did you marry into the village?
4. How many children do you have, and is your eldest a girl or a boy?

Theme 2: Fishing Involvement

1. Were you a fisherwoman? How long have you been fishing?
2. When did you start fishing, and what were you doing before?
3. Did you fish alone or as part of a group most of the time? Was there a difference in experience when fishing alone vs. in a group?
4. Did you *moto*/spearfish in the reef yourself?
5. Was there any special ritual or custom for your first fishing trip? (Follow-up: Are there different rituals if the child is a girl or a boy?)
6. How do you feel about fishing personally? What is your connection to it?
7. Do and how you go fishing in the middle of the passage – for example, with a powered fibreglass boat or *bilibili* (bamboo raft)?

Theme 3: Fishing Practices and Techniques

1. What fishing practices do you use? Are these still practiced today? Where are they practiced – any near or around the reef passages?
2. Are there special fishing practices for certain occasions, or practices unique to Tokou?
3. Where do you usually go to fish?
(Follow-up: Could you show on a map where you fish—inside/outside the passage, on the side, near the reef, or outside the passage? Follow-up: If you refer to the “side of the passage,” what exactly does this mean to you? Follow-up: Where are the lagoons you sometimes mentioned?)
4. Do you use *duva* (traditional fish poison) for fishing, or have you in the past?
5. Have you ever used modern fishing tools or methods introduced through training or shops?
6. What challenges do you face when fishing?
7. Are there any destructive practices or threats to the reefs?
8. Are there resources or support that you feel are lacking for fishing?

Theme 4: Cultural Knowledge, Stories and Totems

1. Are there any stories, legends, sacred places, or guardians associated with the fishing grounds, reefs, or reef passages? (Follow-up: If there are guardians/spirits what are the consequences of not following their rules?)
2. Does Tokou (village/study site) have a totem or special fish?
3. Are there any tabu (forbidden) fish that cannot be caught or eaten? (Follow-up: Who forbids the catching of certain fish (government, *mataqali* (clan), chief)? Why is it forbidden, and is it for the whole village?)
4. Are there fish that must be prepared or cooked in a special way? (Follow-up: Can you describe the stages of Wailo (Wailo, Kava, Kanace, Koto)? Are these the same or different species? Follow-up: What is the story with the Bait - why should one eat it or not?)
5. Are there fish that your husband or children cannot eat?
6. How is this knowledge shared or passed down in the community?
7. Are fishing rules the same across the reef, or are there special rules for the sacred reef passage?

Theme 5: Seasonal Knowledge (Ika ni Yabaki)

1. Which seasonal fish species (Ika ni Yabaki) are present in the reef passages?
2. What are some marine species that you've seen in or pass through the reef passages?
3. Which routes do these species take? Do they come here to spawn?
4. Are there any special practices to follow when these species arrive, or before they arrive?
5. Have you observed whales passing through the passage? (Follow-up: According to you, why do the whales pass here? Follow-up: Could you share more stories or observations related to whales in the passage? Follow-up: You mentioned a whale once got stuck on the reef - how does this relate to the Nalulu passage?)
6. Are there specific seasons for the various fish you catch?

Theme 6: Environmental Change and Observations

1. Are there fish you used to catch that are now rare or have disappeared? Why do you think this is?
2. Have you noticed changes in where women now fish?
3. Have there been any environmental or development changes (e.g., bridges, construction) affecting marine life like kaikoso (shellfish) or mud crabs? Did they disappear and return?
4. Have you noticed changes in tides, currents, or weather patterns that affect fishing?

Theme 7: Fisherwomen's Role in Stewardship

1. How involved are fisherwomen in caring for and managing the reefs and fish (e.g., making decisions about resources)?
2. How would you like to be more involved in reef and marine resource management?
3. How would you protect and look after your marine resources? Do you have any suggestions?

Theme 8: Individual Mapping Activity

1. Please show where you usually fish on a map. Include: inside/outside the passage, on the sides of the passage, near the reef or outside the reef, any lagoons or special fishing spots.
2. Which of your fishing spots are most frequented, and which are less frequented? Label them 1 (most frequent) to 3 (least frequent) and put your initials on each, or you can also use stickers of different colours to differentiate fishing spots. Example: yellow stars indicate the number one fishing spot, green stars indicate the number two spot, pink stars indicate the number three spot, and so on
3. Are there any other stories or observations about the reef passages or your fishing areas that you would like to share?